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Collective beliefs and trust in structured populations

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Abstract

Collective acceptance of narratives can catalyse cooperation in a population of selfish individuals. This effect is present even when the cultural narrative that constitute the belief lack any moralising aspect. Such a narrative catalyst frequently involves a complex system of stories. Hence, it is unlikely to appear in society spontaneously in the same way as actions can change within a generation. Consequently, actions and beliefs can spread at different rates within a population. Besides the process itself, we consider the structure of human populations explicitly. Social and cultural identities often bias the network of interactions. Hence, we develop our model further by assuming a heterogeneous group size and structured population. The person perpetuating a belief might have different degree of connectedness. We aim to understand the speed at which trust builds in a network when the belief originator has low or high connectedness. In this work, we explore the probability, time and dynamics of the spread of trust and beliefs on specific network structures such as a random Erdős and Rényi network, a scale-free Barabasi-Albert network and a small world Watts Strogatz network. Comparing these properties across various network topologies allows us to disentangle the effect of structure, group size diversity and the evolutionary dynamics itself on the evolution of trust and belief.

23 Keywords: structured populations | social evolution | stag-hunt | collective beliefs |
24 targeted mutation | social tipping points

25 Introduction

26 Social interactions are shaped by the experiential histories, convictions and com-
27 mitments of the participating individuals. Individual decisions are not always based
28 solely on facts but often biased by personal beliefs, preferences and constraints (Gin-
29 tis, 2007). The beliefs may develop from events irrelevant to the current decision
30 or may spillover from past experiences (Bednar and Page, 2007; Dolan and Galizzi,
31 2015). The presence of social norms can however stimulate coordination and cooper-
32 ation in a population (Morsky and Akçay, 2019; Gokhale et al., 2022). This effect has
33 been shown to be significant when narratives can spread evenly between individuals.
34 However, not all individuals are as likely to interact with one another. An individual
35 has a higher probability to meet their family, neighbours or co-workers, as compared
36 to strangers living in a different city. In order to account for that, a network structure
37 can be introduced (Santos et al., 2006). The effect of non-moralising collective beliefs
38 on the dynamics on a structured population has not been studied.

39 Cooperation is crucial for development of societies (Axelrod, 1984; Kollock, 1998;
40 Ostrom, 2000). Even though cooperative behaviour yields results desired from the
41 group point of view, it is costly and risky for involved individuals. Game theory can be
42 used to model and understand these instances (Axelrod and Hamilton, 1981; May-
43 nard Smith, 1982; Nowak and Sigmund, 2004). In this work we use the Stag Hunt
44 game (Skyrms, 2003; Pacheco et al., 2009) to illustrate how structure can enhance
45 the emergence and sustainability of trust and cooperation.

46 The dynamics of evolutionary games played by spatially structured populations
47 are shown to differ substantially from their well-mixed counterparts (Abramson and
48 Kuperman, 2001). In particular, the networks are shown to promote and sustain co-
49 operation (Nowak and May, 1992; Santos and Pacheco, 2005; Pinheiro et al., 2012).
50 Although the effect of structure on the level of cooperation has been shown, the inter-
51 play of network and collective beliefs is rarely discussed. Hence, in this work we study
52 how network properties influence game dynamics in presence of distinct beliefs.

53 In this work we study the N-player stag hunt game dynamics in a structured pop-

54 ulation and the effect of collective beliefs. We present simulation results of the game
55 played on various network types and infer the effect of graph attributes on the speed
56 of spread of collaboration. Additionally, we examine the effect of targeted belief muta-
57 tion and consider the existence of social tipping points and the interplay between the
58 critical mass theory with the introduction of structure.

59 **The problem of trust**

60 Trust is a crucial component of social and economic interactions (Fang et al., 2002). It
61 is a foundation of exchanges and contract - entering any agreement is reasonable only
62 if all parties involved believe that others will respect it. Establishing trust would not be
63 difficult to achieve in a risk-free, mutually beneficial setting. However, unfortunately
64 shirking from responsibilities is not uncommon (Skyrms and Pemantle, 2000). Hence,
65 the problem of trust often involves some temptation to break it or risk it not being
66 reciprocated. We define trust as one's conviction that an opponent (or opponents)
67 will work with them towards a common goal (McKnight et al., 1998; Adler, 2001).

68 In order to formalise the problem of trust, we present the following setup: in a
69 tribe of individuals, a group is formed to acquire food. A hunting party consists of N
70 randomly chosen individuals. Each one has an action of hunting a hare or a stag.
71 Pursuing a hare brings a specific, risk-free payoff of $\Pi_H = P_H$ to each hare hunter,
72 where P_H is the value of a hare. For a stag hunt to be successful, at least M stag
73 hunters need to take part. Thus if the number of stag hunters is less than M , then the
74 hunt is unsuccessful, and the payoff of a stag hunter is $\Pi_S = 0$; else, it is $\Pi_S = P_S$.

75 Besides the game as described above, the notion of a collective narrative is in-
76 troduced (Gokhale et al., 2022). Assuming two different narratives, each individual
77 believes in one or the other. Participants of the hunting part decide on which narrative
78 they collectively agree on. Not all participants need to believe in that narrative per-
79 sonally. However, they do condition their actions according to the group's decision.
80 Therefore, each player's strategy consists of three elements -

- 81 • action taken by the individual when the group believes in narrative 1
- 82 • action taken by the individual when the group believes in narrative 2 and,
- 83 • narrative the player personally believes in.

84 For example, a (H,S,1) player would hunt a hare if the hunting party believes in narra-
85 tive 1 and a stag if the party believes in narrative 2. The individual personally believes
86 the narrative 1 to be true. Thus eight different strategies can be present.

87 The model presented in (Gokhale et al., 2022) explains how moral free narratives
88 can influence game dynamics but assumes that the players interact within a well-
89 mixed population. Yet, in a more realistic society, social ties, family connections or
90 geographic closeness can cause specific individuals to interact more frequently than
91 by chance. Similarly, organically formed hunting parties can be expected to include
92 a different number of participants rather than be an artificially chosen, constant size.
93 Varying group sizes can have a significant impact on the game dynamics. Hence this
94 assumption cannot always be substantiated.

95 **Varying group size**

96 The aforementioned model assumes that individuals form groups of a constant size.
97 However, social systems often exhibit group-size heterogeneity (James, 1953; New-
98 man, 2001). Group size diversity can impact the qualitative outcomes of the evolu-
99 tionary games (Peña, 2012; Broom et al., 2018). Therefore we first asses how varying
100 the hunting party size affects cooperation in our model.

101 A mutant strategy can arise in a population consisting of otherwise homogeneous
102 individuals. In the context of human social behaviour, the deviation from the sta-
103 tus quo can be caused by a human's natural inclination to explore available options
104 (Traulsen et al., 2009a). Suppose the change happens with a low enough rate. In that
105 case, the novel behaviour can either take over the population or go extinct before a
106 new type appears. Hence, it is sufficient to analyse the impact of group-size diversity
107 on dynamics between pairs of strategies. In particular, we are interested how the frac-

108 tion of hare hunters ((S,H,2), (H,S,1), (H,H,1) or (H,H,2)) changes when confronted
 109 with stag hunters ((S,H,1), (H,S,2), (S,S,1) or (S,S,2)) in the presence of beliefs.

Considering a pair of strategies (H,H,1) and (S,H,1) is equivalent to a basic N-player stag hunt game with no beliefs involved. We denote the fraction of stag hunters, (S,H,1), as x and the group size as n . Thus the difference between the average payoff of a stag hunter and a hare hunter, $f(x, n)$, is given as,

$$\begin{aligned} f(x, n) &= \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{j} x^j (1-x)^{n-1-j} [\Pi_S - \Pi_H] \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{j} x^j (1-x)^{n-1-j} [P_S \theta(j+1-M) - P_H] \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

110 where $\theta(x) = 1$ for $x \geq 0$ and 0 if $x < 0$.

111 As per Jensen's inequality, (Peña, 2012) show that group size does not affect the
 112 game if $h(x, n) \equiv n f(x, n)$ is a linear function in n . Since $\frac{\partial^2 h}{\partial n^2} \neq 0$ for $n \geq M$, the
 113 stag hunt game will be affected by varying the size of the hunting party. The effect of
 114 changing n is unclear as $h(x, n)$ is neither convex nor concave concerning n .

115 Based on animal group-size distributions we perform a numerical analysis for three
 116 group size distributions - truncated Poisson, geometric, and Waring (Okubo, 1986;
 117 Duerr and Dietz, 2000). In particular, the Waring distribution exhibits power-law de-
 118 gree distribution, a characteristic often obtained by preferential attachment (Albert
 119 and Barabási, 2002). We assume the average group size to be constant across the
 120 cases. Our analysis shows that regardless of the underlying distribution, changing
 121 the group size straightens the cooperation. A similar analysis is performed for all re-
 122 maining pairs of strategies (details provided in Materials and Methods). Except for
 123 two cases ((S,H,2), (S,H,1) and (H,S,1), (H,S,2)), $h(x, n)$ is not linear in n . Hence, it is
 124 reasonable to assume that group size diversity will impact a population's cooperation
 125 (stag hunting) level.

126 Social networks are a natural way of including group size heterogeneity. In our
 127 model, individuals are deployed on a network's vertices, and interactions occur along
 128 the social ties represented by the edges (Santos et al., 2008). Thus, the number
 129 of hunting participants depends on the degree of a given node, and the previously

130 mentioned group size diversity arises from the degree distribution of the graph.

131 **Structured populations**

132 Human societies are represented more accurately by random networks rather than
133 complete ones (Amaral et al., 2000). Many social networks are said to have “small-
134 world” properties (Milgram, 1967; Newman, 2001; Yuan et al., 2011; Wohlgemuth
135 and Matache, 2014), meaning that any two individuals in the network can reach one
136 another via small number of links (steps). Hence in our analysis, we introduce two
137 classes of small-world networks. A small-world network is characterized by a small
138 average path length between two vertices.

139 Erdős and Rényi (Erdős and Rényi, 1960) propose a random network to model
140 real social networks. The network is characterized by a high degree of homogeneity. It
141 is formed by generating n nodes and creating each possible edge in the network with
142 probability p . The Erdős Rényi networks exhibit a low clustering coefficient. Hence, to
143 examine the effect of clustering on the development and spread of trust, we introduce
144 a small-world network generated by the Watts Strogatz algorithm (Watts and Strogatz,
145 1998). A Watts Strogatz network is characterized by a high clustering coefficient and
146 a small average path length between any two vertices. For obtaining such a network,
147 a fraction P of links in a d dimensional regular lattice is deleted and replaced by a
148 random edge.

149 Some members of society are significantly more connected and, as a result, more
150 influential than others. These individuals are represented by hubs - vertices of the
151 network with a high degree. However, the majority of the population is not as well con-
152 nected. Such diversity within the individuals is not present in either of the networks
153 mentioned above. Hence, we use a scale-free network, Barabási-Albert network (Al-
154 bert and Barabási, 2002), with a power-law degree distribution.

155 The Barabási-Albert algorithm is based on preferential attachment. A network
156 grows at each time step by adding one node and connecting it to m nodes already
157 present in the network. A probability of a vertex being connected to the new one is

158 proportional to the attachment function $A(k)$ with k being the node's degree. The
 159 attachment function takes the form of $A_{BA}(k) \propto k$.

160 For the results obtained for networks generated by different algorithms to be com-
 161 parable we keep the network size constant ($Z = 32$) and the average degree approxi-
 162 mately 7.7 (Table 1). The differences in the average degree come from the stochastic-
 163 ity introduced in the generating algorithms. Similarity in the size and average degree
 164 of the networks allows us to focus on the effects of the properties of interest, like the
 165 degree distribution, global clustering coefficient and diameter.

Table 1: Parameters of networks used in simulations.

	Erdős Rényi	Watts Strogatz	Barabási-Albert
Algorithm	Randomly generated edges	Rewiring	Preferential attachment
Size	32	32	32
Average degree	7.79	8.0	7.38
Average number of edges	124.65	128.0	118.0
Parameters	Probability of generating an edge $p = 0.25$	Expected connectivity = 4 Rewiring probability $p = 0.05$	Minimal connectivity $m = 4$
Degree distribution			
Average global clustering coefficient	0.25	0.568	0.313
Average diameter	3.15	3.99	3.02

All networks used in the simulations share the same size and a similar average node degree. The effects of different degree distribution and varying values of clustering coefficient and diameter are of interest.

166 **Updating actions and beliefs**

167 A belief frequently involves a complex system of stories, values, orientation, perspec-
168 tive, and more (Usó-Doménech and Nescolarde-Selva, 2016). Due to its complexity,
169 it is unlikely to appear in society spontaneously at the same rate as new behaviours
170 do. Individuals are far less likely to invent a new belief system or culture, as com-
171 pared to exploring novel behaviours (Boyd and Richerson, 1996). Consequently, we
172 assume that actions and myths appear at different rates. Namely, we introduce two
173 uncorrelated mutation rates - μ_A and μ_B , the former applying to actions taken by an
174 individual (two first elements of the strategy) and the latter influencing the belief (the
175 third element of the strategy).

176 **Dynamics**

177 Our model uses a birth-death Moran process (Nowak et al., 2004; Traulsen et al.,
178 2009b). Every generation consists of Z discrete time steps (Z corresponding to the
179 population size) so that (on average) every individual has an opportunity to repro-
180 duce. In each time step, a belief mutation occurs with probability μ_B - a belief (the
181 third element of the strategy) of a randomly chosen individual is set to one of the two
182 existing narratives, each with equal probability. Subsequently, the fitness of all indi-
183 viduals is determined. A player reproduces with probability proportional to its fitness.
184 The offspring is identical to the parent unless a mutation occurs (with probability μ_A).
185 If a mutation occurs, actions (the first two strategy elements) are drawn from four pos-
186 sibilities (H-H, S-H, H-S or S-S). One of the neighbouring individuals (or the parent
187 itself) is randomly chosen to die and replaced by the offspring.

188 The fitness of an individual (ψ_i) depends on a payoff received after engaging in
189 a hunting game with all their neighbours (π_i) and the selection intensity (ω) (Nowak
190 et al., 2004) as $\psi_i = 1 + \omega\pi_i$. The selection intensity can be used as a proxy for the
191 relative importance of the hunt concerning other activities affecting one's fitness. That
192 is, for $\omega = 0$, the game (and therefore one's strategy) does not affect the fitness and
193 increasing ω enhances the impact of the game on the fitness (Traulsen et al., 2008).

Figure 1: Scheme of the dynamics Strategies are updated by the birth-death process (Bd). An individual is chosen to reproduce with probability proportional to their fitness. A neighbour of the reproducing individual is chosen randomly to die. In each step of the birth-death process a mutation of actions might occur with probability μ_A . Within each generation a belief mutation can take place with probability μ_B . Belief of a randomly chosen individual is randomly set to one of the two narratives present in the population.

194 In the main text, we continue with $\omega = 1$ while different values of selection intensity
 195 are further explored in [Materials and Methods](#).

196 The numerical results presented in this work were obtained for populations of size
 197 $Z = 32$. We choose a population size that could characterize a local hunter-gatherer
 198 residential group ([Bird et al., 2019](#)), but large enough to examine differences in net-
 199 work properties. Initially, all individuals in the population follow the (H,H,1) strategy,
 200 meaning that they always hunt hares and only narrative one is present. As mentioned
 201 above, three types of networks were introduced - Erdős Rényi (ER) with edge gen-
 202 eration probability $p = 0.25$, Watts Strogatz (WS) with expected connectivity of 4 and
 203 rewiring probability $P = 0.05$ and Barabási-Albert (BA) with minimal connectivity of a

204 node $m = 4$. The parameters and properties of the generated networks are specified
205 in Table 1 Each simulation took place for 2×10^5 generations where each generation
206 is Z time steps. We use $\mu_A = 0.001$, $P_H = 1$, $P_S = 4$, $M = 4$, $\omega = 1$. 10 networks
207 were generated for each parameter set and network type, and 100 simulations were
208 run on each. The results presented below are averaged over such 1000 simulations.

209 As per (Santos et al., 2008; Nowak et al., 1994), introducing a structure into a
210 population promotes cooperation. Hence, unsurprisingly, even before introducing a
211 second belief, all simulations result in stag-hunting equilibrium for all types of net-
212 works (achieved by setting $\mu_B = 0.0$). This result differs significantly from the one
213 presented in (Gokhale et al., 2022) where the introduction of beliefs was necessary
214 for the fixation of stag hunters in the population.

215 As the probability of belief mutation increases ($\mu_B = \{10^{-5}, 10^{-4}, 10^{-3}, 10^{-2}\}$),
216 the number of narrative two believers also rises, irrespective of the network type.
217 For mutation rates lower or equal to μ_A fraction of individuals with a heterogeneous
218 ((S,H,1) or (H,S,2)) and homogenous ((S,S,1) and (S,S,2)) strategies are approximately
219 equal. For a higher mutation rate in beliefs ($\mu_B = 0.01$), over 70% of individuals were
220 exclusively stag hunters, regardless of the narrative.

221 A metric of focus for us is the takeover time. We define takeover as the first in-
222 stance when all the individuals in the population are stag hunters. After the takeover,
223 some hare hunters may appear due to mutations; however, they cannot take over the
224 population. In the BA and ER network populations, the takeover happens slower for
225 every considered parameter set than in the WS networks as shown in Fig. 2. This
226 result suggests that a higher clustering coefficient (0.568 for the WS) in the network
227 expedites the spread of cooperative behaviour more effectively, as compared to the
228 lower values (0.25 and 0.313 for ER and BA respectively) (Li and O' Riordan, 2013;
229 Melamed et al., 2018). Although the low network diameter is also said to promote
230 cooperative behaviour (Raghunandan and Subramanian, 2012), the effect is less pro-
231 nounced. Relatively low diameter of 3.15 and 3.02 for ER and BA networks does not
232 lead to a more effective cooperation spread compared with WS network, character-
233 ized with an average diameter of 3.99. In particular, for $\mu_B = 0.0$ (only one narrative

234 present) the average takeover time on the ER network is comparable to BA and over
 235 2.7 times longer than on the WS network.

236 Increasing the value of belief mutation rate μ_B decreases the average time to
 237 takeover on all network types, with a similar reduction of around 70% for ER and BA
 238 and around 45% for the WS. The introduction of beliefs leads to a faster takeover of
 239 cooperative behaviour in the population. The impact of belief is comparable in the
 240 ER and BA networks, which share similar values of average clustering coefficient and
 241 diameter. The impact is less notable for the WS networks. Hence, we hypothesize
 242 that the high clustering coefficient is more effective in promoting cooperation. How-
 243 ever, the beneficial effect of beliefs is amplified more effectively by a lower network
 244 diameter.

Figure 2: Time for stag hunters to takeover the population. The level of action mutation (μ_A) is constant in all simulation runs, hence the change in the mutation rate ratio is caused only by change in belief mutation rate (μ_B). Increase in belief mutation frequency leads to a lower takeover time, meaning that more belief diversity promotes faster spread of cooperators in a population. The takeover is notably faster on the WS networks but the effect of belief is more pronounced on the ER and BA networks. Presented results are averaged over 1000 runs per network type and parameter set.

245 The introduction of structure can notably influence the system's dynamics due to
246 the varying group size and network parameters. While the introduction of different
247 narratives is not required to promote the spread of cooperative behaviour and trust,
248 beliefs can indeed accelerate the process.

249 Hitherto, we assumed that the belief mutation assignment happened at random.
250 Each individual had the same probability of changing their convictions. These as-
251 sumptions are easily violated in reality. The characteristics of network structures can
252 be used to target specific individuals and further accelerate takeover times. In the
253 following section, we analyse how introducing mutations on specific types of nodes of
254 the network influences the dynamics.

255 **Targeting belief spreaders**

256 Not every individual is as likely to be introduced to a novel belief system as others.
257 One's characteristics can influence the probability of exposure to different worldviews
258 or the propensity to internalize a new narrative. In particular, in a structured popula-
259 tion, the connectivity of a node can be an essential factor in determining whether a
260 belief mutation occurs.

261 The concept of changing the properties of a node based on its connectivity is
262 widely explored in epidemiology. A degree of a node, interpreted as a number of so-
263 cial interactions, can be used to identify high-risk individuals ([Christley et al., 2005](#))
264 in order to target them in vaccination campaigns. Targeted vaccination of hubs is
265 intuitive, as they are at a higher risk of getting infected themselves and at spreading
266 the disease. However, vaccination is not the only way in which one's high connec-
267 tivity can be utilized to suppress epidemics. The behaviour of the most connected
268 individuals is essential in determining the fate of the epidemic ([Zhang et al., 2014](#))
269 . Influencing these individuals and raising awareness among them can be used as
270 another outbreak control strategy.

271 The importance of network hubs in epidemiology is apparent. The influence of
272 more connected individuals in a network can also be observed in the context of infor-

273 mation spreading in social networks. However, the involvement of hubs can have the
274 opposite impact, as they can act as “firewalls” and prevent information from spreading
275 (Baños et al., 2013). Hence, it is beneficial to target the less connected “middle-class”
276 nodes in some cases. One of the conditions that might determine the success of the
277 targeting strategy is the network structure in question. Therefore, we aim to examine
278 the effects of considered network types on belief spreading.

279 In our model, the node on which the mutant is introduced is chosen with a degree-
280 based scheme (Teixeira et al., 2021). The probability of being chosen is given by
281 $p_j = e^{\alpha k_j} / \sum_{i \in N} e^{\alpha k_i}$ with k_i being the degree of a vertex i . Parameter α controls the
282 impact one’s connectivity has on its role. In particular, a positive value of α moves the
283 belief mutation to the hubs, $\alpha = 0$ is equivalent to randomly placing the mutant on any
284 node, and $\alpha < 0$ increases the probability of the mutation arising at the periphery.

285 Similarly, for random mutation allocation, all simulations ran with a targeted belief
286 mutation resulted in a stag hunt takeover. Varying values of α did not affect the overall
287 average fraction of each strategy in the population; hence we focus on its effect on the
288 takeover times. We compare the takeover times relative to the random belief mutation
289 placement ($\alpha = 0$).

290 The effect of targeted belief mutation differs notably between different types of net-
291 works, as seen on Fig. 3. For the ER and BA networks, there is a striking distinction
292 between positive and negative values of α (a difference between targeting the hub or
293 the periphery). For the lowest mutation rate $\mu_B = 10^{-5}$ on the BA network (depicted
294 on the bottom panel of Fig. 3), the takeover times for all analyzed values of α do not
295 vary significantly and are shorter than the random case. However, as the mutation
296 rate increases, the differences arise, with negative values of α leading to a similar
297 takeover time as $\alpha = 0$ and positive values - leading to a slower takeover. Differences
298 between parameter values are more visible as the mutation rate increases. This lack
299 of notable differences between negative values of α and $\alpha = 0$ can be caused by the
300 fact that the periphery in the scale-free network is significantly larger than the hubs.
301 Hence, even if the mutation is introduced randomly, it is more likely to occur on a less
302 connected node. This result indicates that on the scale-free network targeting less

303 influential (connected) individuals accelerates takeover.

304 A similar effect can be observed on the ER network (the top panel of Fig. 3). The
305 takeover times for negative values of α are lower than for the positive ones, with all
306 other parameters constant. However, the effect of changing the belief mutation rate
307 value is significantly different. For a small mutation rate ($\mu_B = 10^{-5}$) and all values
308 of α , the takeover is slower than for the random mutation placement. Similar to the
309 results for the BA network, the takeover times for higher mutation and negative values
310 of α converge to values for random mutation placement and positive values of α lead
311 to a slower takeover.

312 The introduction of targeted mutation has a different effect on the WS network
313 (middle panel of Fig. 3). As the degree distribution of nodes is not as divided as in the
314 case of the scale-free network, different values of α do not affect the takeover times
315 in such a diverse way. All non-zero values of α lead to a lower takeover time for a low
316 belief mutation probability. As the mutation value increases, the relative takeover time
317 grows and oscillates around value 1.

318 The impact of targeted belief mutation depends highly on the network type and
319 node degree distribution. For high mutation rates, targeting does not give significantly
320 better effects than randomized placement. However, for a low belief mutation rate
321 it is possible to choose a specific type of individual to introduce new narratives to
322 accelerate the spread of stag-hunting strategies and trust in the population.

323 We have shown that the change in social behaviour is not always induced by the
324 most influential or connected individuals. A committed minority of regular individuals,
325 those who do not hold any significant authority over others, can alter social conven-
326 tions. We thus delve deeper into how different network structures can impact the
327 power of commoners.

328 **Social tipping points**

329 In our model we have shown that less connected individuals can be more effective
330 in spreading the social change, as compared to the well-connected and hence more

Figure 3: Relative time for stag hunters to take over with node targeting. For each value of μ_A/μ_B time to take over is compared to the case of random belief mutation placement ($\alpha = 0$). The impact of varying parameter α is most visible on networks with high node degree heterogeneity (BA and ER) and negligible on the WS network, characterized by high node degree homogeneity. Positive values of α lead to targeting of hubs, which increases the takeover time. The time to takeover can be decreased by targeting the periphery ($\alpha < 0$). Presented results are averaged over 1000 runs per network type and parameter set.

331 influential ones. The importance of the commitment to the cause, rather than the
332 wealth and power of its supporters, is indicated in the critical mass theory (Oliver et al.,
333 1985). According to the theory, a committed minority can produce a "bandwagon"
334 effect and cause a population wide social change.

335 The threshold, which the minority group has to cross in order to ensure a suc-
336 cessful change in the society varies across the literature, ranging from 10% of the
337 population up to 30%-40% (Xie et al., 2011; Centola et al., 2018; Dahlerup, 1988;
338 Grey, 2006). Among others, the value of the tipping point may depend on the under-
339 lying network structure of the population (Centola, 2013).

340 We analyse our results in order to determine an average tipping point value for
341 the network types used and three values of $\alpha = \{-2.0, 0.0, 2.0\}$. The averages and
342 standard deviations of the tipping point are represented in Fig. 4. We assume a given
343 fraction of stag hunters to be a tipping point if after surpassing it for the first time, the
344 proportion did not fall below it. In other words, the population did not reach the tipping
345 point ever before and did not fall below it after crossing it.

346 The effect of belief mutation rate on the average value of the tipping point is promi-
347 nent. Mean and standard deviation increased with increasing mutation rate on all
348 considered network types. This shows that the diffusion of a given strategy can be
349 hindered by introducing a competing minority. With a high mutation rate, a second
350 novel strategy can show up in the population before the takeover by the previous in-
351 vader. Then the increase of a desired strategy can slow down or even be reverted by
352 the new mutant. To ensure that given group is able to grow unhindered, the takeover
353 has to take place before new contender has a chance to appear. With an increase in
354 the mutation rate only a bigger group has an opportunity to takeover the population
355 uninterrupted, leading to a higher value of the tipping point. Hence, we can conclude
356 that if another competing group is not introduced, a minority of around 15 – 30% has
357 enough power to alter the social behaviour of the population. High mutation rates
358 result in increased stochasticity and hence an increase in the mean and standard
359 deviation.

360 The value of the tipping point varies between the WS network and the ER and

361 BA networks, with the value for small mutation and negative α , being 15% for WS and
362 25% and 30% for ER and BA respectively. As shown in Fig. 2 the takeover time on
363 the WS network is shorter compared to other network types. Hence, a single mutant
364 appearing on a network is able to take over faster, reducing the possibility of another
365 invader appearing and hindering the process.

366 The effect of α is not so clearly visible. The differences in values may be caused by
367 the stochasticity present in the system. This parameter does not change the amount
368 of new narrative believers in the population so its impact would not be expected to be
369 exhibited in the tipping point analysis.

370 The study of our results shows that the type of underlying network structure can
371 have a crucial impact on the tipping point value. On networks characterized by high
372 clustering coefficient we observe the tipping point value of 15%. A lower clustering
373 leads to a higher value of the tipping point of around 25% – 30%.

374 Discussion

375 In this study we examine how collective narratives can facilitate spread and sustain
376 cooperation and trust in a structured population of selfish, rational individuals.

377 Introducing structure into a population promotes cooperation (Abramson and Ku-
378 perman, 2001; Santos et al., 2008; Nowak et al., 1994). Specific properties of a given
379 network can further accelerate the takeover by cooperators (stag hunters). A higher
380 value of clustering coefficient leads to a faster takeover. This phenomenon is also
381 observed in presence of beliefs. Moreover, inserting beliefs in a group accelerates
382 the time to takeover by stag hunter. Higher value of belief mutation (causing higher
383 belief diversity) leads to a faster takeover. This effect is additionally augmented and
384 more pronounced in networks exhibiting a low diameter.

385 Properties of an underlying network structure can be exploited in order to facil-
386 itate spread of desired behaviours or attributes in a population. This concept has
387 been utilized in epidemiological studies, which show that the network structure can
388 be used to establish targeted vaccination campaigns. Prioritizing immunization of

Figure 4: Average values of tipping points. The tipping point value for the ER and BA networks are similar, since both types of networks share similar values of parameters. The WS network is characterized by a higher clustering coefficient, which leads to a lower level of clustering. Increasing the value of mutation rate introduces more stochasticity in the system and leads to a higher value of average tipping point and a higher standard deviation value. The parameter α does not have a visible effect on social tipping points. Presented results are averaged over 1000 runs per network type and parameter set.

389 high-contact individuals is shown to have higher effectiveness compared to random
 390 schemes (Yang et al., 2019; Hartnett et al., 2021; Nunner et al., 2022). The effect

391 is especially pronounced on scale-free networks, on which disease spread control is
392 particularly challenging (Pastor-Satorras and Vespignani, 2001, 2002). Zhang et al.
393 (2014) indicate that hubs play a crucial role in epidemic spread control and can ei-
394 ther suppress or promote an outbreak even, if the vaccination scheme is not in place
395 and the only control measure introduced in the model is an individual response to
396 observing the number of infections in the immediate neighbourhood.

397 The crucial role of well-connected individuals can also be utilized for marketing
398 purposes and timely, effective disaster response in social media. Targeting hubs can
399 notably speed up the dissemination of messages (Goldenberg et al., 2009; Fan et al.,
400 2020). However, the effect can also be reversed and the hubs can block the spread
401 of desired behaviour instead of augmenting it (Baños et al., 2013). Tomassini et al.
402 (2007) argue that introducing a mutation on hubs of scale free networks can lead
403 to cascading effects and spread of defectors. Sharma and Traulsen (2022) show
404 that targeting highly connected individuals may lead a graph to lose it's amplifying
405 properties and become a suppressor of selection.

406 In line with these results, our simulations show that introduction of a belief mutation
407 on a periphery of the network can lead to a faster stag hunt takeover when compared
408 to targeting hubs. Hence, targeting individuals with low connectivity is more beneficial
409 then the well connected ones. Notably, this effect is only observable on networks with
410 a differentiable hubs and periphery and is not present in networks with a high node
411 degree homogeneity.

412 Targeting less influential individuals can lead to better effects in promoting coop-
413 eration. We follow up this result by investigating the effect of network structure on the
414 power held by minorities. Low values of belief mutation induce lower average tipping
415 point value. A high mutation value causes introduction of multiple novel strategies at
416 the same time, which might slow down the takeover of a growing, desired minority. In
417 absence of a disadvantage like this, a minority of around 25% is able to cause a social
418 change on ER and BA networks. A change is achieved faster on more clustered WS
419 network, which needs only 15% of propagators to occur.

420 Knowledge of the social network structure is a powerful tool that can be used to

421 predict and influence the behaviour of individuals in the population. Together with
 422 belief systems held by individuals, the structure can be strategically utilized to induce
 423 social change. Introducing novel beliefs to less connected individuals who hold little
 424 power leads to faster diffusion of cooperation in the population. We have highlighted
 425 the properties of the social structure that can be influenced to induce population-wide
 426 changes in beliefs held by minorities. Therefore, raising a positive change in the
 427 population can often be driven by grassroots movements from obscurity.

428 **Materials and Methods**

429 In the following part, three sections are detailed. First, the group size variation anal-
 430 ysis is discussed and results are presented. Then, the definition of the takeover is
 431 reiterated and lastly, the impact of selection intensity is examined.

432 **Varying group size**

433 For any pair of strategies $((a_1, a_2, u)$ and $(a_1^*, a_2^*, u^*))$ the difference between the aver-
 434 age payoffs can be calculated as

$$f(x, n) = \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{j} x^j (1-x)^{n-1-j} \left[\frac{j+1}{n} \Pi_{a_u} + \frac{n-j-1}{n} \Pi_{a_{u^*}} - \frac{j}{n} \Pi_{a_u^*} - \frac{n-j}{n} \Pi_{a_u} \right], \quad (2)$$

435 with x denoting the fraction of players choosing the first strategy.

436 In particular, for a pair of strategies (S,H,1) and (S,H,2), $f(x, n)$ takes a form of:

$$f(x, n) = \frac{P_S - P_H}{n}.$$

437 Hence, it is straightforward to show, that the function $h(x, n) \equiv n f(x, n)$ is linear
 438 with respect to n . Analogous analysis can be performed for strategies (H,S,2) and
 439 (H,S,1). In those cases, the stag hunting strategy dominates the hare hunting, and
 440 the group size does not influence the dynamics (provided, that $n \geq M$).

441 We assume the average group size to be constant across the cases. For $E[N] \approx$
 442 8, $M = 4$, $P_S = 4$, $P_H = 1$ the analysis shows, in Fig. 5, that varying group size
 443 strengthen cooperation, regardless of underlying group size distribution.

Figure 5: Change in dynamics between two strategies depending on the group size distribution. Stag hunting strategies (columns) were compared with hare hunting strategies (rows). Each panel of the plot represents a dynamics between the two strategies, with x representing the fraction of stag hunters. Varying the group size moves the internal fixed point of the dynamics to the left, enlarging the basin of attraction of the all stag hunt equilibrium. Bold frame panels: For pairs (H,S,2), (H,S,1) and (S,H,1), (S,H,2) the dynamics leads to all stag hunt equilibrium regardless of the group size distribution. For each of the considered distributions the parameters are: $E[N] \approx 8$, $M = 4$, $P_S = 4$, $P_H = 1$. Four distributions were considered: fixed group size 8, Poisson distribution with mean $\mu = 8$, geometric distribution with probability parameter $p = 0.111$ and Waring distribution with $\alpha = 2.25$, $\beta = 0.5$, $n = 20$.

444 **Takeover time**

445 As the stag hunt takeover takes place in all the runs, we do not differentiate between
446 takeover times and conditional takeover times. We define takeover as an event when
447 all the individuals in the population are stag hunters. After the takeover, some hare
448 hunters may appear due to mutations; however, they cannot take over the population.

449 **Impact of selection intensity**

450 The importance of the game (interaction) on the overall dynamics can be modelled
451 by varying the value of the ω parameter. For $\omega = 0$ all strategies are equivalent, as
452 the hunt does not influence the fitness.

453 In order to determine the importance of ω on the dynamics, additional set of simu-
454 lations was conducted. We use $Z = 32, \mu_A = 10^{-3}, \mu_B \in \{0.0, 10^{-5}, 10^{-4}, 10^{-3}, 10^{-2}\},$
455 $P_H = 1, P_S = 4, M = 4, \omega \in \{0.0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75\}, \alpha = 0.0.$ Each simulation is run
456 for 10^5 generations. Presented results are averaged over 10 graphs per network type
457 (ER, WS, BA) and 100 runs per graph.

458 As expected, for $\omega = 0.0$ the proportion of stag hunter in the population in a long
459 run is equal to approximately 50% for all values of belief mutation, as there is no
460 advantage to any of the strategies. As the value of the parameter increases even
461 slightly, the proportion of stag hunters grows up to 98%. The effect of belief mutation
462 can be also observed, as the percentage of stag hunters decreases with the mutation
463 rate due to the increase in stochasticity.

464 The same effect is not so visible for abundance of different narrative believers,
465 as the belief itself does not impact one's fitness. Additionally, the belief abundance
466 depends highly on the mutation rate at which the second narrative is introduced. The
467 proportion of narrative believers increases significantly with the increase of $\mu_B.$ A
468 slight increment can also be observed with the growing value of $\omega,$ suggesting, that
469 the presence of the second belief is in fact important for the game dynamic and acts
470 as a coordination device.

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477 **Author contributions**

478 M.F. developed the algorithm and ran the simulations. Both authors conceived the
479 study, developed the model, analysed the results and wrote the manuscript.

480 **Competing interests**

481 The author(s) declare no competing interests.

482 **Data availability**

483 . Appropriate computer code describing the model is available on Github at [https :](https://github.com/tecoevo/structured_beliefs)
484 [//github.com/tecoevo/structured_beliefs](https://github.com/tecoevo/structured_beliefs).

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